

The Influence of Organizational Justice on Organizational Commitment of Instructors in the Public Universities in Amhara Region

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Abstract

The purpose of this study was to examine the influence of organizational justice (OJ) on organizational commitment (OC) of instructors in the public universities of Amhara region. Descriptive survey and correlational research design were employed. The size of the population was 2170. Of these, 740 instructors were taken into the sample using proportional stratified random sampling technique. Standardized questionnaire was used to collect the data. One sample t-test, Structural Equation Modeling (SEM), multiple regression, and one way analysis of variances (ANOVA) were used to analyze the data. The result of one sample t-test indicated that distributive justice was observed moderately while procedural and interactional justice were found to a little extent in the universities as perceived by instructors. With regard to OC, instructors were moderately committed to carry out their jobs due to their emotional attachment with their universities and sense of responsibility. There was a positive and statistically significant relationship between OJ and OC with standardized correlation coefficient ($r=.754$) at $p<.05$. The result of multiple regression indicated that 56.5 % of the variance in OC is explained by the three dimensions of OJ with a significant model $F(3, 736) = 219.952, p= .000$. The result of one way ANOVA indicated that significant differences were observed among instructors in their perception of OJ and OC in the four generations of universities. Therefore, it is concluded that OJ had significant effect on OC of instructors even though procedural justice and interactional justice were observed to a little extent in the public universities in Amhara region. Thus, it is suggested that academic leaders need to improve the current status of procedural justice and interactional justice to make instructors more committed to carry out their duties effectively.

Keywords: Amhara region, Organizational commitment, Organizational justice, Public universities

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Introduction

Background of the Study

It is evident that organizational effectiveness largely depends on various organizational variables. Though there are different factors that have their own contribution to improve the function of organizations, OJ and OC play vital roles in enhancing the performance of the organizations including educational institutions. If a leader wants to improve the performance of an organization, attention must be given to the issues of OJ and OC.

Organizational justice (OJ) is one of the numerous job related attitudes concerned with employees' perception of fair treatment in the organization (Fernandes & Awamleh, 2006; James, 1993). It is conceptualized in terms of distributive, procedural and interactional justice (Cohen & Spector, 2001). Distributive justice is viewed as workers' perception about the fairness of outcomes and its distribution (Toremeh & Tan, 2010). It indicates how employees are fairly rewarded according to their performance (Gilliland, 1994). On the other hand, procedural justice is the fairness of procedures used to determine the outcomes that employees receive (Moorman, 1991). with the quality of interpersonal relationships among employees (Niehoff & Moorman, 1993). It is fostered when decision makers treat people with respect and dignity as well as explain the rationale for decisions carefully. This implies that OJ deals with not only the fair distribution of outcomes but also the fairness of procedures used to determine the outcomes and fairness of interpersonal treatment among employees.

Studies have shown that organizational attitudes and behavior can be directly linked with employees' perceptions of justice (Roch & Shannock, 2006). This means that if employees perceive the outcomes of their evaluations to be fair, they will be likely to respond by performing behaviors to benefit their organization that goes beyond their duties (Niehoff & Moorman, 1993). Employees want to be treated with respect and their contributions to be matched with the outcomes received. Not only do workers want to be equally compensated for their inputs, but they also choose the procedures that delegate outcomes and individuals associated with the delegation of outcomes to be fair as well. When employees perceive that they are fairly treated in the work place, they are more likely to be happy to support their organizations. Similarly, having the procedures that are consistent, unbiased and good interaction between employees and leaders is a basic element for ensuring fairness (Greenberg, 1993; Judge & Colquitt, 2004). On the contrary, employees with the feeling of unfair treatment in an organization will decrease performance, the quality of work and degree of cooperation among workers (Pfeffer & Langton, 1993). This indicates that OJ plays an important role in enhancing employees' level of OC (Robinson, 2004).

OC is another job related component which is viewed as the desire of employees to stay in an organization and get committed towards organizational goals and values. It also refers to the measure of strength of the employees' identification with the goals and values of their organization, having strong faith in it and showing considerable effort to continue in the membership of the organization (Nazari & Emami, 2012; Saglam, 2003). It is measured in terms

of affective, continuance and normative commitment which are related to one another (Allen & Meyer, 1990). Affective commitment refers to an emotional attachment and involvement with an organization while continuance commitment denotes employees' perceived costs associated with leaving an organization (Meyer et al.,1993). Normative commitment denotes an individual's feeling of an obligation to support an organization (Allen & Meyer, 1990).

Committed employees are contented and dedicated and work enthusiastically. Employees with a high level of OC have a strong belief in the goals of the organization and demonstrate high performance to attain the goals of their organizations (Balay, 2000), while organizations that have employees with low level of OC will not be successful in achieving their purposes (Kaya & Selcuk, 2007). Organizations must continually seek ways to keep their employees and work groups effective because the success of the organization depends on its ability to create conditions that attract best people to work there. Turnover rate and absenteeism were high in organizations which had employees with low level of OC (Gerhart & Judge, 1991). This indicates that employees who are committed to their workplace are more likely to exert much effort than employees who have low commitment.

Employees want to stay in an organization as much as they are fairly treated in the system. The findings of many studies indicate that there is a significant relationship between OJ and OC (Kıray, 2011; Shekari, 2011). In an effort to keep employees committed to their job, organizations need to establish a system that treats employees fairly (Akanbi & Ofoegbu, 2013). According to various researchers, employees will remain within the organization when they perceive fair treatment, while the reverse state increases turnover that leads to a decrease in the performance of individuals and reduces the level of OC (Tremblay et al.,, 2010). This shows that OJ has the potential to affect the commitment of employees in organizations (Imamoglu, 2011).

Employees with a sense of equality and the feeling that they are rewarded fairly for their contributions to the organization are satisfied (Srivastava, 2015). Employees who are satisfied with the justice system of their organization will show high level of trust, commitment and performance (Aryee et al.,2002). Individuals with a higher level of OJ perception have a higher commitment to their institutions. In this respect, the results of the study revealed a positive relationship between employees' feeling of justice and commitment (Kıray, 2011; Lambert et al.,2007; Robinson, 2004; Yazıcıoğlu & Topaloglu, 2009). Employees will be committed to serve their organization when are treated properly by their leaders. .Similarly, the findings of McFarlin and Sweeney (1992) indicated that fair treatment of employees resulted in employees' desire to reciprocate by demonstrating behaviors that benefit the organization. In addition, employees who feel mistreated in the workplace incline to show deviant behavior and decrease the possibility to engage in OCB (Vardi & Wiener, 1996).

Based on the discussions made so far about OJ and OC as well as their relations, a new conceptual framework was synthesized for this study as indicated in Figure 1. The framework considers distributive justice, procedural justice and interactional justice as the dimensions used to measure an OJ construct. Similarly, affective commitment, continuous commitment and normative commitment are considered as the dimensions used to measure an OC construct.

Figure 1*Proposed conceptual framework of the study***Statement of the Problem**

Currently there appears to be an increasing interest among scholars in OJ and OC. OJ and OC are important factors linked to the success of any organization. This indicates that employees with feeling of fair treatment and high level of commitment in organizations tend to be effective in carrying out their duties compared to other employees with the feeling of unfair treatment and low commitment. Thurston and McNall (2010) claimed that the feeling of fairness is considered as an important position in decision making process concerning rewards, benefits and other compensation issues. Fairness in pay received, decisions about the reimbursement process and the way this information is communicated to all employees are significant about the compensatory system (Milkovich & Newman, 2008).

Employees who perceive unfair treatment may have negative effect on the effectiveness of organizations. Numerous studies conducted in the past pointed out that employees exhibit workplace aggression (Kennedy et al.2004) due to lack of fair treatment in organizations. These situations lead to increase turnover intention and interpersonal deviance (Cohen & Spector, 2001), exhibit counter productive work behavior (Spector & Fox, 2002) and burnout, turnover, absenteeism and low productivity (Colquitt et al.,2001; Janssen, 2004) as well as low commitment, and eventually, they may pursue to leave the organization (Aslam et al.,2016). These indicate that employees who are deprived of justice in organizations will be susceptible to stress, dissatisfaction, lower level of commitment, frequent absenteeism, and aggression leading to low productivity.

Concerning commitment, the findings of many studies indicate that low level of commitment leads to turnover and attrition (Joiner & Bakalis, 2006; Meyer et al.,2002), absenteeism (Farrell & Stamm, 1988), counterproductive behavior (Dalal, 2005), and decline in altruism and compliance (Schappe, 1998). A survey conducted by Bosman et al.(2008) showed

that high level of employee turnover was associated with poor function of an organization and increased the cost involved in selecting and training the replacements. These can cause loss of work progress, productivity, organizational status and poor relationship with customers (Alzubi, 2018). High turnover rates can increase the cost of recruitment, training and retention of staff (Al-Hussami, 2008), as well as negatively affect the success of the organization in attaining strategic objectives, sustaining competitive advantage, and keeping the morale, productivity and quality of work in the organization (Alzubi, 2018). Mobley (1982) also described employee turnover as a serious problem facing many organizations including educational institutions.

Although some studies have been conducted on OJ and OC (Alemu, 2014; Endale, 2019; Endris & Dawit, 2019; Temesgen, 2011; Tesfaye, 2004), sufficient studies have not been done on the causal relationship between these variables in the context of Ethiopian higher education institutions in general and in the public universities of Amhara region in particular. This study, therefore, examines the influence of OJ on OC of instructors in the public universities of Amhara region. Thus, the following research questions are formulated to guide this study.

1. What is the perception of instructors towards OJ and OC in the public universities of Amhara region?
2. What is the relationship between OJ and OC in the public universities of Amhara region?
3. What are the influences of OJ dimensions on OC in the public universities of Amhara region?
4. Are there significant differences among instructors in perception of OJ and OC in the four generations of universities in Amhara region?

Significance of the Study

This study may generate empirical evidences about the status of OJ and OC in the public universities of Amhara region. It may create awareness on the part of academic leaders about the importance of OJ and OC in supporting the function of public universities. In addition, it may also contribute to the body of literature in the areas of OJ and OC in the context of Ethiopian higher education institutions. Moreover, the study may provide first-hand information about the result of OJ in enhancing instructors' commitment. Furthermore, it attracts the attention of policy makers and practitioners with regard to OJ and OC so that they can suggest the ways in which employees will be committed and feel good about their job. Moreover, less attention has been given to the issue of OJ and OC in Ethiopian higher education institutions; thus, the findings of this research may initiate other researchers to conduct further studies.

Delimitation of the Study

This study covered six public universities in Amhara region that were selected from the 1st, 2nd, 3rd and the 4th generations and focused on academic staff because academic staff are believed to have better understanding about the issue under investigation than supportive staff. With regard to variables, the study was delimited to OJ and OC. Specifically, OJ was measured in terms of distributive justice, procedural justice and interactional justices from the perspectives

of instructors (Cohen & Spector, 2001; Moorman, 1991). Instructors' level of OC was measured using three dimensions – affective commitment, continual commitment and normative commitment as was developed by Meyer et al.(1993). In addition, the establishment of universities was considered to check whether significant differences were found among instructors in their perception of OJ and OC.

Method

Design

Since this research aimed to assess instructors' perception about the status of OJ and OC as well as examine the relationship between these variables, descriptive survey and correlational research design were found appropriate. Therefore, descriptive survey and correlational research design were used as a guide using quantitative methodology.

Research Setting

This research was conducted in six public universities of Amhara region that were selected from the 1st, 2nd, 3rd and the 4th generations. These generations which contain universities with nearly similar characteristics such as infrastructures, staff profiles, academic programs, and so on were considered as strata.

Participants

Categorized into four generations based on years of establishment, there are 10 public universities in Amhara region. These are two universities from the 1st generation, three from the 2nd generation, two from the 3rd generation, and three from the 4th generation. Of these, six universities were selected from the specified strata for manageability reason. That is, University of Gondar from the 1st generation, Wollo and Debre Markos Universities from the 2nd generation, Debre Tabor University from the 3rd generation, and Injibara and Debarq Universities from the 4th generation were selected using stratified random sampling technique. These stratifications allowed to ensure the representation of universities from each generation and make comparison among respondents in their perception of OJ and OC.

Then, a total of 21 colleges were selected from the six universities to determine the size of the population and subpopulations of the study. Specifically, five colleges from University of Gondar, four from each of Wollo, Debre Markos, and Debre Tabor Universities, and two from each of Injibara and Debarq Universities were selected using simple random sampling technique through lottery method. In this regard, a total of 2170 instructors found in the selected universities were taken as the population of the study. Of the total size of instructors, 731 from the 1st generation, 710 from the 2nd generation, 427 from the 3rd generation, and 302 from the 4th generation universities were considered as the subpopulations of the study.

Although there is no single criterion that determines the necessary sample size, Comrey and Lee (1992) suggested that the sample size with 500 and above would be good to carry out factor analysis. Based on the suggestions of Raykov and Marcoulides (2006) and Tabachnick and Fidell (2007), 20 respondents per each item were used in the present study to determine the size of the sample. Accordingly, the sample size of this study was 740 since the number of items under the dimensions of the variables in the questionnaire was 37. After determining the total sample size of the study, the sample size of each stratum was determined based on the size of their population using proportional sample allocation method developed by Pandey and Verma (2008). This helps to select representative samples from each stratum with the assumption that numbers of instructors in the selected strata significantly varied. Hence, the sample size of each stratum was determined through dividing the population size of the k^{th} stratum by the total population size and multiplying by the total sample size using Pandey and Verma (2008) formula as given below. i.e.

$$n_k = \left(\frac{N_k}{N} \right) * n$$

Where;

n_k = Sample size of k^{th} stratum

N_k = Population size of the k^{th} stratum

N = Total population size

n = Total sample size

Of the total sample of 740 instructors, 249 from the 1st generation, 242 from the 2nd generation, 146 from the 3rd generation, and 103 from the 4th generation universities were taken into the sample using proportional stratified random sampling technique. The summary of population and sample of the study are shown in Table 1 below.

Table 1

Summary of population and sample of the study

Strata	Name of universities	Population size of each university (N_k)	Sample size of each university (n_k)
1 st generation	University of Gondar	731	249
	Wollo University	280	95
2 nd generation	Debre Markos University	430	147
3 rd generation	Debre Tabor University	427	146
	Injibara University	145	49
4 th generation	Debark University	157	54
	Total	$N= 2170$	$n= 740$

Instruments

Standardized questionnaire was used to collect the data with the intention to increase the reliability of the results. The questionnaire had three parts containing close ended items. The first part of the questionnaire consisted of an item related to respondents' universities where they were working. The second part of the questionnaire contained 19 items developed by Moorman (1991) and Niehoff and Moorman (1993) with the intent to assess respondents' feelings towards OJ in the workplace. These items were organized into three dimensions such as distributed justice, procedural justice and interactional justice. The third part of the questionnaire measured respondents' perceptions about OC. It was measured using 18 items organized in three dimensions developed by Meyer et al. (1993): affective commitment, continual commitment, and normative commitment.

Finally, respondents rated items using five points Likert type scales ranging from 1 (not at all) to 5 (to a very great extent) to measure OJ and OC in the workplace.

Validity and Reliability of the Questionnaire

The validity of the questionnaire was checked using theoretical support of relevant literatures and technical evaluation of research experts in relation to face and content validity. In this regard, face validity was evaluated through my colleagues about the appearance of the questionnaire in terms of feasibility, readability, consistency of style and formatting, and the clarity of the language used. Based on the given comments, problems related to the clarity of language, uniformity of style and formatting of the questionnaire were improved. The content validity of the questionnaire was also evaluated by the research advisors. Hence, the organization of the questionnaire related to relevance, simplicity and wording of items were adjusted based on the feedback obtained from the research advisors. In addition, statistical technique was used to test the content validity of the questionnaire using content validity index formula of Lawshe (1975). After items were identified to be included in the final questionnaire, content validity index was calculated for the mean of the content validity ratio values of the retained items. Thus, the content validity indices of items are .91 and .85 for OJ and OC respectively indicating that items were valid to measure their respective latent variables and dimensions.

Reliability is another aspect of quantitative research that was measured. Pilot test was conducted on 90 selected instructors of Bahir Dar University to assess the reliability of the questionnaire. The distribution of sample for pilot test followed the same procedures as in the main sample of the study. Cronbach Alpha was used to test the internal consistency of items. The reliability coefficients of the dimensions of the instruments as estimated by Cronbach Alpha (α) range between .87 and .94 for OJ and between .82 and .88 for OC. This indicates that items in the respective dimensions with reliability coefficients $\geq .80$ are considered as internally consistent to measure OJ and OC (George & Mallery, 2010).

Data Analysis Techniques

Inferential statistical analysis techniques were used to analyze the data using SPSS software version 23. Specifically, a one sample t-test was used to measure the status of OJ and OC in the workplace (Research question #1). SEM was used to assess the relationship between OJ and OC (Research question #2). Multiple regression was used to analyze the effect OJ dimensions on OC of instructors (Research question #3). Finally, one way ANOVA was used to assess whether instructors differ in their perception of OJ and OC in the four generations of public universities in Amhara region (Research question #4).

Ethical considerations

Initially, permission letter was sought from Bahir Dar University to collect the data from the research sites. Based on the given permission, the list of target respondents was accessed and the required samples were identified before starting to collect the data. Then, the researcher provided information for the research participants so that they could understand the purpose of the study before they took part in the study. Participants were also informed about the absence of both potential risks and benefits due to participation in the study. In addition, the collected data were confidential and anonymous in order to keep the rights of the research participants. Moreover, respondents were informed that their involvement in the study was totally voluntary and that they would withdrawal from the research at any time. More importantly, any communication with concerned bodies was not carried out without the consent of the research respondents. Finally, the questionnaire was distributed to the sample respondents, and they were given three days to fill the questionnaires.

Results

This section presents the results of the study according to the themes of the research questions. It begins with testing the construct validity of the respective dimensions of latent variables and measurement model fit through conducting exploratory and confirmatory factor analyses.

Factor analysis

Although there is no clear criterion to decide what is large or small, items with factor loadings $\pm.33$ and above are considered to meet the minimum level of threshold based on the recommendation of Ho (2006). The result of exploratory of factor analysis indicated that all items in the respective dimensions of OJ and OC had high factor loadings above the cutoff point of $\pm.33$ which accounted for 10% of the total variances of variables. In this case, 32 items heavily loaded on the dimensions of OJ and OC with factor loading values ranging from .628 to .877 were retained, and they contributed more than 50% of the variance in OJ and OC constructs.

However, five items with low factor loadings were discarded from the analysis, for they suppressed the reliability of OJ and OC. This has reduced the number of items in the variables from 37 to 32. The results of principal component analysis also showed that the factor loadings of OJ and OC dimensions with eigen values ranging from 1.464 to 3.896 were greater than the minimum threshold of 1.

Based on the results of the construct validity, the three dimensions of OJ (distributive justice, procedural justice, and interactional justice) and three dimensions of OC (affective commitment, continuance commitment, and normative commitment) were identified as indicators. Taking the identified dimensions of the two latent variables, the measurement model was constructed using AMOS version 23 as shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2

Measurement model of the study

After testing the construct validity, confirmatory factor analysis was carried out to assess the parameter estimates of the latent variables and the overall fit of the measurement model to the data. Although there is little agreement among scholars on the type of fit indices and their cutoff points, relative chi-square (CMIN/DF), goodness of fit index (GFI), adjusted goodness of fit index (AGFI), normed fit index (NFI), incremental fit index (IFI), Tucker-Lewis index (TLI), comparative fit index (CFI) and root mean square error of approximation (RMSEA) were used to evaluate the fitness of the measurement model to the data. Accordingly, absolute and incremental fit measures such as CMIN/DF values less than <3 (Kline, 2005) and GFI, AGFI, NFI, IFI, TLI and CFI values greater than .90 (Ho, 2006) were considered as the cutoff point to assess the measurement model of this study. Finally, RMSEA value lower than .05 was used as the criteria to assess the overall fit of the proposed measurement model (Byrne, 2010). Thus, summary of goodness of fit indices to assess the measurement model are indicated in Table 2.

Table 2

AMOS outputs on the fitness indices against the criteria of the measurement model

Criteria	Obtained values	Threshold
Relative chi-square (CMIN/DF)	2.580	<3
Goodness of fit index (GFI)	.988	>.90
Adjusted goodness of fit index (AGFI)	.968	>.90
Normed fit index (NFI)	.978	>.90
Incremental fit index (IFI)	.984	>.90
Tucker-Lewis index (TLI)	.971	>.90
Comparative fit index (CFI)	.984	>.90
Root mean square error of approximation (RMSEA)	.044	<.05

As indicated in Table 2, the measurement model satisfied all of the fit indices. That is, the results indicated that the measurement model fits to the data by the χ^2 ($N = 740$, $df = 8$) = 20.644, $p < .05$. In addition, the fit indices of GFI (.988), AGFI (.968), NFI (.978), IFI (.984), TLI (.971) and CFI (.984) were higher than the threshold of .90, and a RMSEA (.040) was lower than the cutoff of point .05 with $p = .022$. This indicates that the possible improvement of the measurement model ranging from .012 to .032 appears to be as small as of little practical significance.

The maximum likelihood estimates of regression and standardized regression weights confirmed that all the path coefficients in the model are significant at $p < .05$ as shown in Table 3.

Table 3*Unstandardized and standardized regression weights of the measurement model*

Parameters/dimensions	Unstandardized				Standardized		
	Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P	Estimate		
Distributed justice	<---	OJ	.428	.053	8.081	***	.363
Procedural justice	<---	OJ	.574	.050	11.380	***	.553
Interactional justice	<---	OJ	1.000				.763
Affective commitment	<---	OC	.663	.041	16.059	***	.615
Continuous commitment	<---	OC	.882	.045	19.707	***	.774
Normative commitment	<---	OC	1.000				.850

As it has been indicated in Table 3, the unstandardized regression weights of all the dimensions of OJ and OC are significant with the critical ratio test greater than ± 1.96 at $p < .05$. From this, it is possible to conclude that the critical ratio tests of the six dimensions are far away from the threshold of ± 1.96 which indicates a significant path at $p < .05$.

Likewise, the standardized regression weights also ensured the significance of the dimensions of the latent variables. The standard regression estimates of all the six dimensions were significantly represented by their respective latent variables. Specifically, the standardized regression weights of the observed variables in the measurement model ranged from .363 (distributive justice) to .850 (normative commitment). This implies that the observed variables explained the respective latent constructs ranging from 13.2% (distributive justice) to 72.3% (normative commitment). These values indicated that OJ and OC were significantly measured by their respective dimensions at $p < .05$. This shows that all dimensions in the measurement model are internally consistent and structurally valid to measure OJ and OC.

Status of Organizational Justice and Organizational Commitment

Table 4

A one sample t-test for the dimensions of OJ and OC

Dimensions	Mean	Std.	Test value	Mean difference	t-value	Sig.(2-tailed)
Organizational justice						
Distributive justice	13.49	2.797	12	1.486	14.455	.000
Procedural justice	10.99	3.954	15	-4.008	-27.572	.000
Interactional justice	19.51	4.004	21	-1.493	-10.146	.000
Organizational commitment						
Affective commitment	22.19	5.753	18	4.195	19.834	.000
Continuance commitment	15.48	4.621	18	-2.516	-14.811	.000
Normative commitment	14.89	3.359	12	2.893	23.433	.000

N=740, df = 739, *Sig. <.05

The results in Table 4 indicated that the mean score of distributive justice (13.49) is greater than the test value at ($t = 14.455$). The positive mean difference and t-value also confirm that the observed mean score is significantly higher than the test value at $p < .05$, $df = 739$. This means that instructors fairly perceived the state of distributive justice in the workplace. On the other hand, the mean scores of procedural justice (10.99) and interactional justice (19.51) are less

than the respective test values at ($t = -27.572$) and ($t = -10.146$) respectively. The respective negative mean differences and t values of these dimensions ensure that the obtained mean scores are significantly lower than the test values at $p < .05$, $df = 739$. This indicates that procedural justice and interactional justice are observed to a little extent in the universities.

With regard to OC, the results of one sample t test indicated that the mean scores of affective commitment (22.19) and normative commitment (14.89) are higher than the respective test values at $t = 19.834$ and $t = 23.433$. The positive mean differences and t -values also confirm that the observed mean scores are significantly greater than the test values at $p < .05$, $df = 739$. This implies that instructors are moderately committed to carry out their job due to their emotional attachment with their universities and sense of responsibility to serve their universities. Conversely, the mean score of continuance commitment (15.48) is lower than the test value at $t = -14.811$. The negative mean difference and t value of this dimension prove that the obtained mean score is significantly lower than the test value at $p < .05$, $df = 739$. This means that instructors are committed to a little extent to perform their job due to continuous commitment.

The Relationship between Organizational Justice and Organizational Commitment

Table 5

Standardized Correlation Coefficient of OJ and OC

Latent variables			Unstandardized				Standardized
			Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P	Estimate
OJ	<-->	OC	.658	.054	12.238	***	.754

As can be seen from Table 5, positive and statistically significant relationship is observed between OJ and OC with standardized correlation coefficient ($r = .754$) by the critical ratio test greater than ± 1.96 at $p < .05$. This implies that the commitment of instructors increases when there is OJ in the workplace.

The Influence of Organizational Justice on Organizational Commitment of Instructors

Table 6*Regression of organizational commitment on the dimensions organizational justice*

Dimensions of OJ	Adjusted R Square	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		
		B	S.E.	Beta	t-value	Sig.
Constant		1.272	.091		13.947	.000
Distributive justice	.565	.503	.021	.634	23.687	.000
Procedural justice		.091	.013	.185	6.859	.000
Interactional justice		-.105	-1.84	-1.85	-6.827	.001

As shown in Table 6, the results of multiple regression indicated that 56.5% of the variance in OC is predicted by the three dimensions of OJ with a significant model at $F(3, 736) = 219.952, p = .000$. The values of regression coefficient are found significant as .634, .185 and -1.85 for distributive justice, procedural justice, and interactional justice respectively. This shows that all dimensions of OJ significantly contribute to predict OC although they do not have equal contribution in explaining OC. In nutshell, the rest 43.5% of the variation in OC is attributed to the residual variances that cannot be explained.

One Way ANOVA for University Generations

Table 7

One way ANOVA on differences in perception of OJ and OC among instructors in the four generations of universities

Variables	Generations of universities	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
OJ	Between Groups	190.763	3	63.588	49.989	.000
	Within Groups	936.215	736	1.272		
	Total	1126.978	739			
OC	Between Groups	124.201	3	41.400	32.624	.000
	Within Groups	933.983	736	1.269		
	Total	1058.184	739			

As shown in Table 7, the result of one way ANOVA indicated that there are statistically significant differences among instructors in their perception of OJ at $F(3, 736) = 49.989$, $p = .000$ and OC at $F(3, 736) = 32.624$, $p = .000$ in the four generations of universities. The mean scores of the 1st, 2nd, 3rd and 4th generation universities in the four variables also confirmed that instructors differ in their perceptions of OJ and OC. This shows that instructors in the four generations of universities perceived the status of OJ and OC differently.

Although the F-ratio indicates significant differences among instructors in their perception of OJ and OC in the four generations of universities, it did not indicate the location of these differences. As a result, post hoc analysis was computed using Scheffé test to identify which generations of universities differed significantly from each other at .05 level of significance. This is shown in Table 8 below.

Table 8

Post hoc tests of multiple comparisons among instructors in perception of OJ and OC

Variables	(I) Generations of universities	(J) Generations of universities	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.	95% Confidence Lower Bound	Interval Upper Bound
OJ	1 st	2 nd	.1969	.1056	.325	-.0990	.4930
		3 rd	-1.1330*	.1129	.000	-1.4494	-.8166
		4 th	.0909	.1259	.914	-.2620	.4438
	2 nd	1 st	-.1969	.1056	.325	-.4930	.0990
		3 rd	-1.3300*	.1196	.000	-1.6652	-.9948
		4 th	-.1061	.1319	.886	-.4759	.2637
	3 rd	1 st	1.1330*	.1129	.000	.8166	1.4494
		2 nd	1.3300*	.1196	.000	.9948	1.6652
		4 th	1.2239*	.1378	.000	.8376	1.6103
	4 th	1 st	-.0909	.1259	.914	-.4438	.2620
		2 nd	.1061	.1319	.886	-.2637	.4759
		3 rd	-1.2239*	.1378	.000	-1.6103	-.8376
OC	1 st	2 nd	.47632*	.1055	.000	.1807	.7720
		3 rd	-.60118*	.1128	.000	-.9172	-.2852
		4 th	.46349*	.1258	.004	.1110	.8160
	2 nd	1 st	-.47632*	.1055	.000	-.7720	-.1807
		3 rd	-1.07750*	.1195	.000	-1.4123	-.7427
		4 th	-.01283	.1318	.892	-.3822	.3566
	3 rd	1 st	.60118*	.1128	.000	.2852	.9172
		2 nd	1.07750*	.1195	.000	.7427	1.4123
		4 th	1.06467*	.1377	.000	.6788	1.4506
	4 th	1 st	-.46349*	.1258	.004	-.8160	-.1110
		2 nd	.01283	.1318	.892	-.3566	.3822
		3 rd	-1.0647*	.1377	.000	-1.4506	-.6788

The results of Scheffé test indicate that instructors in the 1st generation universities are significantly different from instructors in the 3rd generation universities in perception of OJ. On the contrary, instructors in the 2nd and 4th generation universities do not differ significantly from the 1st generation universities in perception of OJ. Significant differences are observed between instructors in the 2nd and 3rd as well as between the 3rd and 4th generation universities in perception of OJ. But, instructors in the 2nd generation universities do not differ significantly from instructors in the 4th generation universities in their perception of OJ.

With regard to OC, the results of Scheffé test reveal that instructors in the 1st generation universities are significantly different from instructors in the 2nd, 3rd and 4th generation universities in perception of OC. Significant differences are also observed between instructors in the 2nd and 3rd as well as in the 3rd and 4th generation universities in perception of OC. However, instructors in the 2nd generation universities do not differ significantly from instructors in the 4th generation universities perception of OC.

Discussion

The findings of this study indicated that OJ was observed in public universities to some extent or to a little extent. Specifically, distributive justice is found moderately in the workplace while procedural justice and interactional justice are observed to a little extent as shown in Table 4. This finding is similar to the works of Awang and Ahmad (2015) and Nguni et al.,(2006) that distributive justice is observed to some extent in the workplace. Other researchers also reported that distributive justice is moderately observed in the organizations (Mahrani et al.,2013; Wajde et al., 2018) that enable employees rewarded fairly according to their contribution. The findings of Gulluce et al.(2015) and Wajdee et al. (2018) are similar to the result of the current study as regards procedural justice and interactional justice.

With regard to OC, the finding of this study indicated that instructors have moderate level of affective commitment and normative commitment; however, they have low level of continuous commitment in their universities. The works of Endale (2019), Temesgen (2011) and Tesfaye (2004) are similar to the findings of this study related to affective commitment and normative commitment. In the same way, the findings of Endris and Dawit (2019), Mahrani et al. (2013) and Gulluce et al. (2015) are also similar to the findings of this study concerning affective and normative commitment. With regard to continuous commitment, research conducted by Mahrani et al. (2013) indicated that employees demonstrated a modest level of continuance

commitment in the workplace. The result of this study is further supported by the findings of other studies on the status of continuance commitment as perceived by employees (Karanja, 2016). This shows that employees' commitment is affected by different factors.

Employees want to stay in the organization as much as they are fairly treated in the system. The result of this study indicated that there is a significant relationship between OJ and OC. This finding is congruent with a result of Ghafari and Golparvar's (2009) study that OJ had positive and significant correlation with OC because the staff perceive their leaders to be fair, respectful and unbiased in their dealings. Kıray (2011) and Shekari (2011) also found a significant relationship between OJ and OC. This indicates that employees with the feeling of fair treatment have high level of commitment in the workplace. Similarly, other studies conducted in different organizations indicated that OJ is significantly related to OC (Cameran et al., 2007; Lemons & Jones, 2001; Yazıcıoğlu & Topaloglu, 2009). Moreover, a finding of this study is consistent with the finding of Robinson (2004) that there is a positive and significant relationship between OJ and OC. When employees' rewards are equal to the inputs, they develop the feeling of fair treatment while the reverse situation leads to a state of mistreatment. Employees become committed when they develop the feeling of fair treatment; however, the opposite feeling does not bring this result (Imamoglu, 2011).

Justice is vital if employees are to be committed to the organization. The findings of the previous studies also indicated that OJ had significant effect on OC similar to the findings of the current study. Concerning this, Imamoglu (2011) reported that OJ had significant effect on OC. In the same way, other researchers also supported the significant influence of OJ on employees' level of commitment in the workplace (Cropanzano et al., 2007; Demir, 2011). Moreover, the findings of other studies proved that employees' perceived justice had significant effect on employees' commitment towards their job (Rezaiean et al., 2010). Therefore, it is possible to say that the fairness of outcomes distributed within the organization and its function improve the level of commitment of employees to the organizations.

Furthermore, the finding of the current study that OJ is an important factor determining employees' commitment in the workplace is congruent with the works of Ogunyemi and Ayodele (2014) and Sarnecki (2015). Likewise, various studies conducted in various areas proved that OC tends to improve for those employees whose leadership gives them the opportunity to partake in decision-making (Steyrer et al., 2008). The findings of other studies also indicated that staff who were satisfied with the way they were treated by their leaders were

committed to the organization (Aryee, et al., 2002; Baotham, 2011). This finding was consistent with that of Bakhshi et al.(2009) and Mowday et al. (2013) who reported that fairness in organization makes employees committed in the workplace.

This study has some limitations First, since it used a new conceptual framework, sufficient literature related to OJ and OC has not been found in the context of higher education institutions in general and Ethiopian public universities in particular. Because of this, literatures reviewed related to these variables in the context of other organizations are used for the purpose of this study. The other limitation of this study was that it has considered only the academic staff working in the public universities in Amhara region due to time and resource constraints. As a result, the findings of this study may not be generalized to all Ethiopian public universities. Shortage of recent studies related to OJ and OC in the context of higher education institutions was also another limitation of this study

Conclusions and Implications

Conclusions

Based on the results obtained, the following conclusions are drawn.

- The dimensions of OJ such as procedural and interactional justice are observed to a little extent, while distributive justice is found moderately in the workplace as shown in Table 4. With regard to OC, affective commitment and normative commitment are observed to some extent, but continuous commitment is found to a little extent as perceived by instructors.
- There is a positive and statistically significant relationship between OJ and OC with standardized correlation coefficient ($r = .754$) at $p < .05$ as indicated in Table 5.
- The results of multiple regression indicate that 56.5 % of the variance in OC is predicted by the three dimensions of OJ, while the rest 43.5% of the variance in OC is attributed to the residual that cannot be explained (See Table 6).
- As shown in Table 7, there are statistically significant differences among instructors in their perception of OJ and OC in the four generations of universities.

Implications

To improve the current status of OJ and OC, academic leaders at all levels need to give high attention to the issue of employees' justice and commitment in order to enhance the performance of their institutions. Academic leaders also need to improve the current status of procedural and interactional justice through validating the fairness of procedures used to make decisions and interpersonal treatment in the institutions. Instructors shall be committed enough to serve their institutions without considering perceived costs associated with their job. Moreover, further studies need to be conducted on OJ and OC in the context of Ethiopian higher educational institutions to broadly generalize the results that will be obtained.

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